

Rac-4c

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-162-rac-20%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	6	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 162 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/27/2021 4:27:05 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/28/2021 10:42:13 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.316	7376925	50.62	698200
2	8.178	7197318	49.38	616340

Asy-4c

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-157-20%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	28	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 157
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/27/2021 5:03:34 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/28/2021 10:43:59 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.351	712143	2.70	67228
2	8.208	25682876	97.30	2187961